

Towards a Generic Knowledge Graph Construction Framework for Privacy Awareness

Christina Karalka, Georgios Meditskos, Maria Papoutsoglou, Nick Bassiliades
School of Informatics, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki,
Thessaloniki, Greece
{kchristi, gmeditsk, mpapo, nbassili}@csd.auth.gr

Abstract—Knowledge graphs (KGs) organize data from multiple sources, capturing information about entities of interest in a given domain or task, such as people, places, or events, and forge connections between them. In this paper, we introduce a generic framework for building knowledge graphs designed to enhance data privacy through semantic interpretation. We demonstrate the effectiveness of our framework by applying it to the healthcare sector, where it helps organize and analyze complex information, support data analysis, improve decision-making processes, and uncover hidden relationships between entities. Our approach leverages domain-specific ontologies like SNOMED CT and integrates vector databases to assess and mitigate privacy risks. By using semantic techniques, we enhance the robustness of data against reidentification attacks and suggest appropriate deidentification methods. The integration of SNOMED with vector databases allows for efficient storage, retrieval, and analysis of high-dimensional healthcare data, facilitating advanced data analytics and knowledge discovery while maintaining data privacy. Through this framework, we aim to provide sufficient insights for identifying privacy vulnerabilities and ensuring the security and usability of sensitive health information.

I. INTRODUCTION

Knowledge Graphs [1] are a type of knowledge base founded on the principle of applying a graph-based abstraction to data with their construction typically grounded in Semantic Web (SW) technologies [2]. SW encompasses a collection of models and languages with diverse expressive capabilities, forming a layered infrastructure for data representation and utilization. Its foundation constitutes the Resource Description Framework (RDF) aiming to establish a universally accepted standard where a specific domain can be effectively modelled through a set of assertions [3]. Consequently, the fundamental unit of information is a statement, represented as an ordered triple of entities or resources. These statements collectively establish a data model structured as a directed multi-relational graph with nodes representing specific entities, ranging from individuals to places or objects. Semantic connections between these entities are depicted as edges linking the nodes, thus providing an organized representation of complex relationships and concepts.

The organization and interpretation of data in a KG are guided by the principles and constraints specified in an ontology. Often considered as the schema of the KG, an ontology serves as a formal and explicit representation of knowledge within a specific domain [4]. Ontologies include definitions of high-level concepts (entity categories or classes) and properties

(attributes and relationships), often organized in hierarchical structures. This machine-readable representation is empowered by languages like OWL (Web Ontology Language), a recommended standard by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). OWL empowers the articulation of intricate relationships and complex modelling patterns, extending beyond simple hierarchical structures. By expressing domain semantics in this manner, it enables automated reasoning, thereby enhancing knowledge discovery, inference, and decision-making. Furthermore, established axioms, expressed as restrictions in OWL, play a vital role in identifying inconsistencies, consequently elevating the quality and reliability of the data.

Furthermore, a shared understanding of data can be established by reusing existing ontologies that define common, domain-specific vocabularies. These conceptual frameworks capture complex interdependencies among fine-grained terms within a particular field, providing a unified language for data interpretation that enhances interoperability and simplifies the exchange of intelligence across different organizations. Furthermore, such ontologies have undergone extensive review, and refinement by domain experts over an extended period, ensuring data quality.

The utilization of knowledge graphs offers a transformative approach to enhancing privacy-related aspects in data handling and analysis, particularly within sensitive domains such as healthcare. By structuring data relationships without explicitly storing identifiable information, knowledge graphs inherently anonymize sensitive data, reducing the risk of privacy breaches. Advanced data anonymization and masking techniques ensure that outputs do not expose personally identifiable information (PII) or protected health information (PHI) [5]. Furthermore, knowledge graphs enable fine-grained access control, allowing for precise permissioning and minimizing unauthorized data exposure. This controlled access, coupled with automated compliance with privacy regulations such as GDPR and HIPAA, ensures that data handling processes adhere to legal standards and protect individual privacy.

Additionally, knowledge graphs facilitate improved data aggregation and synthesis, allowing users to gain insights from high-level data abstractions without needing access to raw, detailed datasets [6]. This capability minimizes the exposure of sensitive information while still providing valuable analytical outcomes. Implementing differential privacy within knowledge graphs further enhances privacy by injecting noise into data

queries, preserving the utility of the dataset while protecting individual data points. Context-aware privacy controls, transparency, and auditability of data usage, along with enhanced data integrity and security measures, collectively ensure that sensitive information is robustly protected. By leveraging these capabilities, knowledge graphs not only enhance privacy but also build trust among users and stakeholders, promoting ethical and compliant data usage across various domains.

To date, several domain specific knowledge graphs have been created. For example, Auer et al. [7] present a general KG for the science domain, Wang et al. [8] have created a KG for the social engineering in cyber security domain, while Zhang et al. [9] present a semi-automatic framework for graph construction for the healthcare domain. In this paper, we introduce a framework designed for the construction of knowledge graphs. Our framework, in contrast to the state-of-the-art, is designed to be generic, enabling its application across a wide range of domains. However, to demonstrate its utility and effectiveness, we specifically focus on its application within the healthcare domain. Through this application, we illustrate how our framework can be leveraged to construct knowledge graphs that effectively capture and organize information pertinent to healthcare. As such, the underlying semantics can be leveraged to help stakeholders evaluate privacy-preserving technologies aiming for efficient and intelligent data use in privacy-preserving contexts.

This paper outlines the theoretical underpinnings of our framework for generating Knowledge Graphs, its design considerations, and the practical steps involved in implementing it for healthcare knowledge graph construction, along with a discussion on the implications and potential benefits of our approach.

II. RELATED WORK

Recent advancements in SNOMED CT post-coordination for clinical information extraction show great potential. However, manual construction of these expressions is challenging due to complex terminology and a lack of specialized tools. KGE4SCT, a novel method using knowledge graph embeddings (KGEs), addresses this by suggesting post-coordinated expressions for clinical terms, achieving notable accuracy in various aspects, including a semantic type accuracy of 98% and a relationship accuracy of 90% for the Spanish SNOMED CT version [10]. Additionally, the healthcare industry's need for high-quality remote services, accentuated by the COVID-19 pandemic, has led to the adoption of knowledge graphs integrating standards such as SNOMED CT, ICD-10-CM, and DOID ontology, to enhance disease detection and assistance systems [11]. Furthermore, an automated knowledge graph curation framework for neurological diseases like subarachnoid hemorrhage has shown promising results in concept extraction and prediction accuracy [12]. Lastly, methodologies for building Health Condition Evolution Statements (HES) databases from public sources using SNOMED CT taxonomy have also emerged, emphasizing human-in-the-loop models to ensure high-quality knowledge graph construction [13].

Effective data mining in the medical domain is crucial due to the diverse nature of real-world data. Traditional models using homogeneous graphs struggle to uncover varied relationships among data elements. An innovative classification model utilizing a heterogeneous knowledge graph from the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) data shows promising results in knowledge discovery and health risk classification [14]. In connected care, AI models on IoT devices and wearables capture biomedical data, requiring uniform descriptions. The DAHCC ontology and knowledge graph integrate sensor data and AI algorithms with patient health insights, enabling AI application reuse without burdening healthcare professionals. A dataset of 42 participants annotated with DAHCC demonstrates its potential in connected care [15]. Additionally, personalized healthcare applications need to integrate knowledge from IoT devices and EMRs. The proposed Personalized Healthcare Knowledge Graph (PHKG) addresses these challenges, synthesizing meaningful information for chronic disease management [16]. Finally, a novel model organizes heterogeneous textual medical knowledge (TMK) into conceptual graphs, significantly enhancing knowledge retrieval and inference with high precision and recall in automated graph utilization [17].

III. HEALTHCARE DOMAIN SPECIFIC ONTOLOGIES

In the healthcare domain, two widely used examples of domain specific ontologies are the SNOMED clinical terms [18] and the semantic DICOM ontology [19]. SNOMED CT (Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine - Clinical Terms) is a multilingual clinical terminology and ontology system developed by SNOMED International (or Health Terminology Standards Development Organization). It is designed to serve as a comprehensive and standardized system for encoding clinical information in electronic health records (EHRs) and other healthcare applications. Its intricate hierarchy addresses a multitude of medical domains, encompassing a wide range of concepts related to medicine and healthcare. This expansive coverage empowers healthcare professionals and institutions by providing a robust system for precise and consistent clinical data representation, thereby enhancing the quality of patient care and medical research.

SNOMED CT functions as an extensive clinical taxonomy, with 19 top-level concepts (see Figure 1) serving as foundational branches within the subtype hierarchy. These categories name and anchor their respective subhierarchies, encompassing a plethora of similar entities. Each subtype maintains a hierarchical connection to the top-level concepts through at least one sequence of "is-a" (subclass of) relationships. As the hierarchies descend, concepts progressively acquire greater specificity and granularity.

At the same time, The DICOM standard defines an extensive coding system for encoding metadata associated with medical images. Specifically, each data element is uniquely identified by a specific code and tag name. These identifiers are organized into modules that collectively describe various aspects of the image or study, including image acquisition

Fig. 1. The list of the top-level concepts in SNOMED CT (left). The concept hierarchy of the “Myocardial infarction” class (middle) with a list of synonyms defined through the *skos:altLabel* annotation property (right).

parameters, patient demographics, anatomical references, and diagnostic findings. For instance, the code (0010,0030), which corresponds to the tag name “Patient’s Age”, falls within the broader “Patient Module (0010)” group. Complementing the DICOM standard is the Semantic DICOM Ontology (SeDI), developed by SOHARD Software as part of the “SeDI – Semantic PACS” project and hosted on BioPortal. SeDI introduces a systematic framework aimed at enhancing the contextual understanding of DICOM-encoded data. At the center of its conceptual model lies the pivotal class of “Information Object Definition” (IOD), serving as the linchpin for distinguishing and characterizing the nature of DICOM objects. This overarching concept encompasses multiple subclasses tailored to specific types of DICOM data, such as “MRI Image” and “Ambulatory ECG”. The categorization of DICOM objects is determined by the value of the “SOP Class UID” (Service-Object Pair Class UID) attribute, an indicator of different medical data types such as various imaging modalities and clinical reports.

IV. SEMANTIC ANNOTATION AND KG GENERATION FRAMEWORK

The objective of the proposed framework is the development of an ecosystem that will support the generation, validation, and usage of ontologies and knowledge graphs, with the aim of facilitating privacy-preserving processing of similar data types across organizations and sectors in a semantically interoperable manner. More specifically, through the introduction of a semantic layer that operates on top of the existing data sources, this component enables the interlinking, enrichment, and harmonization of data from diverse sources, enabling the effective exchange of data and intelligence. The utilization of formal Semantic Web standards and domain-specific ontologies fosters the establishment of a semantically interoperable framework,

promoting consistent and standardized data representation and interpretation. The proposed architecture encompasses several key components designed to realize these objectives which are illustrated in Figure 2 and summarized as follows:

- Beginning with the Input Standardization Module, the initial step involves the transformation of heterogeneous input data representations into a standardized format. This is achieved by extracting an intermediate ontology graph (Putative Ontology–PO) from the input schemas, setting the foundation for further operations.
- The subsequent Mapping Generation Module plays the pivotal role of discovering semantic correspondences between the elements of this new representation with resources modeled in a selected domain-specific ontology (DO).
- The resulting alignments serve as the basis for aligning the two ontologies and establishing hierarchical relationships between their corresponding elements. Finally, the resulting ontology undergoes refinement and is populated with data from the initial data source, culminating in the generation of the Knowledge Graphs.
- In addition to these fundamental components, a final section delves into a use-case-specific preprocessing procedure focused on the expansion of abbreviations and acronyms in the medical sector.

Fig. 2. Overview of the main components of the semantic annotation and KG generation framework for the healthcare domain.

V. RESULTS

We apply the previous framework to create KGs in two medical domains that are detailed in the rest of this section.

A. Electronic Patient Record

The first input data source within the health use case is a patient record dataset in tabular format. Its primary focus is on cardiovascular health, making it a valuable resource for researchers and healthcare professionals specialized in cardiac-related conditions, treatments, and patient outcomes. Each row in this dataset corresponds to an individual patient, resulting

in a total of 164 dimensions that collectively capture various aspects of patient health and medical history.

Columns like age, height and BMI offer a profile of the patients’ physical characteristics. Prescribed pharmaceutical interventions are also documented, including medications like ACE inhibitors and sartans. Medical conditions and symptoms are thoroughly examined, encompassing issues like dyspnea, angina, myocardial infarction, and diabetes management. Additionally, the dataset includes quantitative metrics derived from lab test results, such as lipid levels and blood sugar measurements. Furthermore, it incorporates results from medical tests like electrocardiograms and echocardiograms, as well as outcomes from exercise stress tests designed to assess cardiac health and fitness. Notably, a significant emphasis is placed on the condition of various arteries, such as the left main coronary artery, and whether these arteries have undergone medical interventions such as bypass grafting.

A distinctive characteristic of this dataset is its significant utilization of medical abbreviations and acronyms (AAs). Precisely, 78% of the total columns incorporate at least one AA. Consequently, the management of this dataset necessitates the introduction of an additional pre-processing step within the semantic annotation pipeline. This step enhances the disambiguation process by expanding these abbreviated terms. A total of 63 columns containing AAs were deemed to have been interpreted properly, with the majority consisting of acronyms. The expansion of abbreviations proved more challenging, with a 53% success rate and 33% of cases remaining unexpanded. The handling of ad-hoc contracted forms remains an open issue, with 30 columns presenting high levels of ambiguity for non-experts. These expanded forms were integrated into the corresponding PO resources as alternate labels, utilizing the `skos:altLabel` annotation property. Subsequently, the Mapping Generator facilitated the alignment of the enriched PO elements with classes from the SNOMED CT ontology. We opted for the BioBERT variant of BERT as the language model of the classifier.

Figure 3 demonstrates some indicative mapping results. Listed in Group 1 are several headers that exhibited perfect compatibility, either by being mapped with a BERTMap Equivalence Score of 1 or by having a single highly confident match. Also falling into this category are headers containing abbreviations in Group 2. Notably, the mapping of these columns was only successful upon expanding their abbreviated forms, highlighting the significance of the expansion step. Additionally, Group 3 lists headers that, despite having multiple candidates, exhibited minimal ambiguity. In contrast, Group 4 encompasses headers with candidates that are intricately related and represent a highly detailed level of granularity, making it challenging to make a definitive selection. Resolving this ambiguity remains an open issue. To emphasize this point, the PO class of the respective column is denoted as a subclass of the union of these candidates. An example of this modelling pattern is depicted in Figure 4 for the LAD1 column.

Group 1	
age , angina , arteropathy , blood sugar , dyspnea , dyslipidemia , exam date , height , hypoglycemic time , hypertension , notes , sex , smoking , stress , stroke/TIA , therapy , result , watt , weight	
Group 2	
ACS: Acute coronary syndrome , Alterations ECHO: Echocardiogram abnormal , BMI: Body mass index , BPCO: Chronic obstructive lung disease , CAD: coronary artery disease , Family history of CAD, CABG: Coronary artery bypass grafting , ECGbasal: Electrocardiogram , ECGstress: Electrocardiogram with exercise test , Hgbt: Hemoglobin , HDL: High density lipoprotein , MI: Myocardial infarction , Nitg: Nitroglycerin , LDL: Low density lipoprotein , PCR: Polymerase chain reaction	
Group 3	
Header	SNOMED CT Mapping
EF_ECHO	Echocardiography (Pr)
MI_2	History of type 2 myocardial infarction (Si)
Dilatation LV	Dilatation of left cardiac ventricle (Di)
PCIstent	PCI - Percutaneous coronary intervention (Pr)
Hypertrophy LV	Left ventricular hypertrophy (Di)
Group 4	
CX1	Stenosis of proximal portion of circumflex branch of left coronary artery (Di) Occlusion of proximal portion of circumflex branch of left coronary artery (Di)
LAD1	Structure of anterior descending branch of left pulmonary artery (BS) Structure of anterior descending branch of left coronary artery (BS)
Diabetes	Lipoatrophic diabetes (Di) Diabetes insipidus (Di) Diabetes mellitus (Di)

Fig. 3. Indicative results of the semantic annotation task for the electronic patient record dataset. Each object is accompanied by the URI of the selected SNOMED CT class. Pr denotes “Procedure”, Di “Disorder”, BS “Body Structure”, Si “Situation” of the top-level concepts in the SNOMED CT taxonomy.

Fig. 4. Sample Knowledge Graph generated from one row and two columns of the first dataset in the health use case.

B. DICOM Images

The second dataset for the health use case comprises a collection of DICOM image files. This dataset includes various DICOM types, such as Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), Computed Tomography Scan (CT), Secondary Capture Imaging (SCI), and X-Ray Radiation Dose SR. Among these types, MRIs are the most prevalent. Such a medical image is associated with metadata that takes the form of a nested dictionary whose attributes adhere to the DICOM tagging scheme. The SeDI ontology serves as the conceptual framework for modelling these metadata into a knowledge graph.

For each DICOM file in the dataset, an instance of the appropriate subclass of the “Information Object Definition” container class is generated based on the value of the SOP Class UID. This object is then associated with Information Entities, where metadata information is logically distributed. Figure 5 illustrates the schema of the Knowledge Graph specifically designed for MR Image objects. An instance of this class is linked to a patient, characterized by personal information, and serving as the subject of the medical study.

The study itself is timestamped to reflect the date of examination and involves the participation of an attending physician. Specialized equipment was employed to acquire a series of MR images, with each image providing a unique perspective of the patient’s anatomy and possessing distinct visual attributes. Notably, certain attributes are exclusive to specific imaging modalities, such as ‘Echo Number’ for MRIs. Lastly, the attributes of the ‘Frame of Reference of MR Images’ object ensure spatial alignment and consistency among sequential MR images.

Fig. 5. KG schema tailored to MRI data. The central element is the “MR Image” Information Object Definition. This object is associated with specialized Information Entities highlighted with blue. Each entity is characterized by a set of attributes expressed by datatype properties and listed in their respective frames. Positioned above each entity is its immediate parent class, enclosed within a green box.

Figure 6 depicts the graph section generated for a specific MRI object, with an emphasis on the management of sequence attributes. Two distinct types of sequences have been linked to the Image Information Entity object through object properties, that collectively express their respective Sequence DICOM codes. Each nested object within the sequence is represented by an Item of the corresponding type and encompasses a set of attributes. For instance, the “Anatomic Region Sequence” is a structured data element used to describe the anatomical region or body part that is the subject of a medical image. Lastly, the items within the Referenced Image Sequence establish associations with related images.

VI. TOWARDS ASSESSING DATA PRIVACY THROUGH SEMANTICS

The semantic interpretation of data sources plays a crucial role in identifying key variables and assessing privacy risks, ultimately strengthening data against reidentification attacks. By clarifying attributes with well-defined classes and properties, ontologies facilitate the selection of suitable de-identification methods. For example, dates can be obscured through noise injection (perturbation), and personal names can be completely removed (redaction). Furthermore, taxonomy relations help generalize rarely occurring values (generalization hierarchy) [20]. Privacy vulnerabilities are identified through a collaboration of automated techniques and domain experts. At the

Fig. 6. KG schema tailored to MRI data. The central element is the “MR Image” Information Object Definition. This object is associated with specialized Information Entities highlighted with blue. Each entity is characterized by a set of attributes expressed by datatype properties and listed in their respective frames. Positioned above each entity is its immediate parent class, enclosed within a green box.

data level, graph analysis techniques exploit the underlying graph structure of the knowledge graph (KG) to infer indirect identifiers from outlier combinations. Concurrently, domain knowledge is encoded in a predefined rule set to effectively combine, associate, and interpret the information in KGs, gaining contextual insight and identifying privacy issues. This method allows the system to suggest the implementation and configuration of privacy-preserving technologies based on the type of data being processed. For instance, an indirect link between a creditor and a debtor could raise privacy concerns when combined with other information and should be reported to the data owner. Similarly, in healthcare data, the association between a rare medical condition and a specific demographic group could lead to reidentification risks and must be carefully managed to protect patient privacy.

Our solution uses SPARQL to execute CONSTRUCT graph patterns to detect problematic situations, defined as SHACL Rules on top of domain ontologies like SNOMED. This allows us to identify sensitive links between treatments and conditions that may disclose patient information. Using SNOMED ensures data privacy while allowing meaningful analysis of health records. By applying semantic techniques, we can better identify and mitigate privacy risks in health datasets, enhancing their security and usability.

Integrating SNOMED with vector databases and large language models (LLMs) significantly enhances the capacity to assess data privacy through semantics. Vector databases enable efficient storage and retrieval of high-dimensional representations of data, which can be particularly beneficial when dealing with complex healthcare datasets. When combined with SNOMED’s comprehensive medical ontology, this setup allows for precise and scalable analysis of health data. Large language models, trained on vast amounts of medical literature, can further augment this framework by understanding and generating insights from unstructured data sources, such as clinical notes and patient records. These models can automatically identify sensitive information and suggest appropriate de-

identification techniques based on context, improving both accuracy and efficiency. For example, an LLM can detect indirect identifiers within patient narratives and cross-reference these with SNOMED terms stored in a vector database, ensuring a robust privacy-preserving strategy. This integration not only bolsters the protection of sensitive health information but also facilitates advanced data analytics and knowledge discovery in the healthcare domain.

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper we presented a generic framework for knowledge graph construction. To verify its effectiveness we applied it to the healthcare domain, providing two specific examples. In our future work, we plan to further integrate Large Language Models (LLMs) to enhance the performance and accuracy of our results. Additionally, we are exploring new techniques to improve the efficiency and reliability of Knowledge Graphs, ensuring more effective data processing. We also aim to utilize the SNOMED-CT vector database to refine the generative process and increase the relevance of LLM outputs in the health domain. Additionally, a challenge we faced was the different meanings of health abbreviations present in the raw data. We handled this issue using an abbreviation expansion modeling approach, but in future steps, we plan to integrate this approach further with the support of language models. Specifically, we plan to create an automated process to efficiently handle abbreviation disambiguation. This will involve leveraging advanced natural language processing techniques to dynamically interpret and expand abbreviations based on contextual clues within the clinical text. By doing so, we aim to enhance the accuracy and reliability of our clinical information extraction system. Finally, to enhance the productivity and accuracy of the knowledge graph results in combination with the use of large language models (LLMs), we plan to create an annotated dataset. For the annotation process, we will recruit healthcare practitioners to evaluate the produced results. This dataset will then be used to create a benchmark for testing against raw data. Additionally, we will test the updated framework to determine its capability to support the creation of knowledge graphs in different domains. By incorporating expert evaluations and benchmarking, we aim to ensure the robustness and generalizability of our approach across various medical and non-medical fields. This will not only improve the current system but also pave the way for broader applications of knowledge graphs.

VIII. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research has received funding from the Horizon Europe Framework Program under Grant Agreement No 101070670 (ENCRYPT). The content of this publication reflects the opinion of its authors and does not, in any way, represent opinions of the funders. The European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information that this publication contains.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Fensel, U. Şimşek, K. Angele, E. Huaman, E. Kärle, O. Panasiuk, I. Toma, J. Umbrich, and A. Wahler, *Introduction: What Is a Knowledge Graph?* Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2020, pp. 1–10.
- [2] N. Shadbolt, T. Berners-Lee, and W. Hall, “The semantic web revisited,” *IEEE Intelligent Systems*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 96–101, 2006.
- [3] S. Decker, P. Mitra, and S. Melnik, “Framework for the semantic web: an rdf tutorial,” *IEEE Internet Computing*, vol. 4, no. 6, pp. 68–73, 2000.
- [4] B. Chandrasekaran, J. Josephson, and V. Benjamins, “What are ontologies, and why do we need them?” *IEEE Intelligent Systems and their Applications*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 20–26, 1999.
- [5] C. Sun, F. Igne, G. Spinaci, G. Amaral, J. Domingue, K. Kurniawan, and M. G. Ocana, “Privacy-protection within the evolution and preservation of knowledge graphs: The vad2er approach towards medical citizen science.”
- [6] I. Khokhlov and L. Reznik, “Knowledge graph in data quality evaluation for iot applications,” in *2020 IEEE 6th World Forum on Internet of Things (WF-IoT)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [7] S. Auer, V. Kovtun, M. Prinz, A. Kasprzik, M. Stocker, and M. E. Vidal, “Towards a knowledge graph for science,” in *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Web Intelligence, Mining and Semantics*, ser. WIMS '18. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2018.
- [8] Z. Wang, H. Zhu, P. Liu, and L. Sun, “Social engineering in cybersecurity: a domain ontology and knowledge graph application examples,” *Cybersecurity*, vol. 4, pp. 1–21, 2021.
- [9] Y. Zhang, M. Sheng, R. Zhou, Y. Wang, G. Han, H. Zhang, C. Xing, and J. Dong, “Hkgb: An inclusive, extensible, intelligent, semi-automated knowledge graph framework for healthcare with clinicians’ expertise incorporated,” *Information Processing Management*, vol. 57, no. 6, p. 102324, 2020.
- [10] J. Castell-Díaz, J. A. Miñarro-Giménez, and C. Martínez-Costa, “Supporting snomed ct postcoordination with knowledge graph embeddings,” *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, vol. 139, p. 104297, 2023.
- [11] A. De Nicola, R. Zgheib, and F. Tagliano, “Toward a knowledge graph for medical diagnosis: issues and usage scenarios,” in *Semantic Models in IoT and eHealth Applications*. Elsevier, 2022, pp. 129–142.
- [12] K. M. Malik, M. Krishnamurthy, M. Alobaidi, M. Hussain, F. Alam, and G. Malik, “Automated domain-specific healthcare knowledge graph curation framework: Subarachnoid hemorrhage as phenotype,” *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 145, p. 113120, 2020.
- [13] A. C. Morales Tirado, E. Daga, and E. Motta, “Towards a knowledge graph of health evolution,” in *International Conference on Knowledge Engineering and Knowledge Management*. Springer, 2022, pp. 105–120.
- [14] X. Tao, T. Pham, J. Zhang, J. Yong, W. P. Goh, W. Zhang, and Y. Cai, “Mining health knowledge graph for health risk prediction,” *World Wide Web*, vol. 23, pp. 2341–2362, 2020.
- [15] B. Steenwinckel, M. De Brouwer, M. Stojchevska, J. Van Der Donck, J. Nelis, J. Ruysinck, J. van der Herten, K. Casier, J. Van Ooteghem, P. Crombez *et al.*, “Data analytics for health and connected care: Ontology, knowledge graph and applications,” in *International Conference on Pervasive Computing Technologies for Healthcare*. Springer, 2022, pp. 344–360.
- [16] A. Gyrard, M. Gaur, S. Shekarpour, K. Thirunarayan, and A. Sheth, “Personalized health knowledge graph,” in *CEUR workshop proceedings*, vol. 2317. NIH Public Access, 2018.
- [17] L. Shi, S. Li, X. Yang, J. Qi, G. Pan, and B. Zhou, “Semantic health knowledge graph: semantic integration of heterogeneous medical knowledge and services,” *BioMed research international*, vol. 2017, no. 1, p. 2858423, 2017.
- [18] M. Q. Stearns, C. Price, K. A. Spackman, and A. Y. Wang, “Snomed clinical terms: overview of the development process and project status.” in *Proceedings of the AMIA Symposium*. American Medical Informatics Association, 2001, p. 662.
- [19] J. Van Soest, T. Lustberg, D. Grittner, M. S. Marshall, L. Persoon, B. Nijsten, P. Feltens, and A. Dekker, “Towards a semantic pacs: Using semantic web technology to represent imaging data,” *Studies in health technology and informatics*, vol. 205, p. 166, 2014.
- [20] E. Purificato, S. Wehnert, and E. W. De Luca, “Dynamic privacy-preserving recommendations on academic graph data,” *Computers*, vol. 10, no. 9, p. 107, 2021.